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Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **G**rape, **O**Live and **D**urum wheat food systems

Deliverable 3.5

A handy easy-to-use manual for stakeholders and practitioners of the climate service tool.

PART II: the grape/ wine sector

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Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This user guide is designed to provide documentation for people who will use the climate service tools developed in the frame of the MED-GOLD project for the wine sector. The purpose of this manual is to provide all users of the provided services with a reference manual containing step-by-step instructions on how to log-on, use the tool, download and interpret the results.

The material in this manual includes instructions for the climate service tool (MED-GOLD Dashboard) provided for the wine sector. The MED-GOLD Dashboard is a web-based application that allows the users to easily visualise, interact and even download climate data and indices.

The aim of the climate service tools is to enable the end-users to adapt their decision making strategies to the climate conditions and climate change.

1. OBJECTIVES

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	X
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	

2. IMPACT

No.	Expected impact	Yes
1	Providing added-value for the decision-making process addressed by the project, in terms of effectiveness, value creation, optimised opportunities and minimised risk	The user manual is essential for promoting and exploiting the developed climate services of the project, since it provides all the necessary information to the end-users (farmers, agronomists, policy makers, scientists) to guide and encourage them to use the tool and take full advantage of the product.
2	Enhancing the potential for market uptake of climate services demonstrated by addressing the added value	
3	Ensuring the replicability of the methodological frameworks for value added climate services in potential end-user markets	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	

3. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Concept / Term	Definition
Dashboard	Web-based application that was developed to apply climatic services to the agricultural sectors of MED-GOLD project
Tercile	Division of the population distribution into three categories
Above normal tercile	The highest 33% of values (those below the upper tercile)
Normal tercile	Centred around the middle value between lower and upper terciles
Below normal tercile	The lowest 33% of values (those below the lower tercile)

4. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Acronym	Definition
CSV	comma-separated values
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathways
CDS-C3S	Climate Data Store of the Copernicus Climate Change Service
GST	Growing Season Temperature
SprR	Spring Rainfall
HarvestR	Harvest Rainfall
SU35	number of days with Tmax > 35°C
WSDI	Warm Spell Duration Index
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
ERA5	ECMWF Atmospheric ReAnalysis 5
PTHRES	Dataset provided by University of Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro

5. REFERENCES

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document. They are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]:

Ref.	Title	Code	Version	Date
[RD.1]	MED-GOLD Deliverable 3.2: Report on the methodology followed to implement the wine pilot services			2020
[RD.2]	MED-GOLD Deliverable 3.6: First feedback report from users on wine pilot service development			2019
[RD.3]	MED-GOLD Deliverable 3.7: Second Feedback report from users on wine pilot service development			2020
[RD.4]	Research paper: High-Resolution Temperature Datasets in Portugal from a Geostatistical Approach: Variability and Extremes. Fonseca, A.R., and Santos, J.A. (2017). J.			2017

	Appl. Meteor. Climatol. 57, 627–644. https://doi.org/10.1175/JAMC-D-17-0215.1			
[RD.5]	Research paper: The ERA5 global reanalysis. Hersbach et al. (2020). Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society. https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3803			2020
[RD.6]	Research paper: SEAS5: the new ECMWF seasonal forecast system. (2019) Johnson, Stephanie & Stockdale, Tim & Ferranti, L. & Balmaseda, Magdalena & Molteni, Franco & Magnusson, Linus & Tietsche, Steffen & Decremer, Damien & Weisheimer, Antje & Balsamo, Gianpaolo & Keeley, Sarah & Mogensen, Kristian & Zuo, Hao & Monge-Sanz, Beatriz.. Geoscientific Model Development. 12. 1087-1117. 10.5194/gmd-12-1087-2019 .			2019

6. MED-GOLD DASHBOARD FOR THE WINE SECTOR

Climate change is causing extreme weather events, such as droughts and heat waves. In recent years, it has become a real challenge for grape growers and wine producers. In the future, with the continuation of climate change, anticipating these events will be essential in adapting to the wine sector.

The MED-GOLD dashboard is an easy-to-use visualisation tool, which provides access to information on past climate and predictions of future climate at different time scales. The tool has been co-developed with users to ensure that it addresses their needs and expectations. On the Dashboard we can consult for different times scales, essential variables - where are represented monthly temperature (minimum, maximum and mean) and monthly precipitation - bioclimatic indices - take into account the climate and the phenology of the vine - and wine risk indicators , this risk indices show the possibility of exist sanitary risk (disease) or heat risk (Fig. 6-1).

Figure 6-1: Scheme of data information you can access on the Dashboard.

6.1. GENERAL INFORMATION

The objective of information in the tool is to provide users with the possibility of adapting / mitigating the effects of climate change, providing support on decisions.

The methodology of the co-design and co-development adopted, including the rounds of interactions with users, has been described in [RD.1, RD.2, RD.3]. The climate data shown along with all the technical

details are described in [RD.1]. All these deliverables are available in <https://www.med-gold.eu/documents-deliverables/>.

All the instructions about the use of the MED-GOLD Dashboard, including the below reported use cases, have been described in the infosheet “*The MED-GOLD Dashboard for the wine sector*” available in <https://www.med-gold.eu/documents-publications/>, also translated in portuguese, spanish and greek, and here reported in Annex A.

6.2 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

In this section, how you can access and obtain the information you need for your activities will be explicitly explained. This will be explained, step-by-step, from the moment you login until you get the information you need for the desired location and time scale.

6.2.1 USER ACCESS

You can access the dashboard on the MEDGOLD website, and by visiting: <https://dashboard.med-gold.eu>. The accounts should be requested contacting the MED-GOLD Consortium partners or med-gold.project@enea.it. The login access page is shown in Figure 6-2.

Figure 6-2: Login access page of <https://dashboard.med-gold.eu>

Sign in to your account

Username *

Password *

Forgot your password? [Reset password](#)

No account? [Create account](#)

SIGN IN

After login this is what you should see (Fig. 6.3) (Note: information for Douro valley of historical climate for december 2015 appears by default).

Figure 6-3: Dashboard Homepage

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Figure 6-4: Homepage of Dashboard with sections numerated.

6.2.2 LANDING MENU TABS

In the MED-GOLD Dashboard you can access three different times scales; on section No 2 in Figure 6.4, you can select one of the three tabs: historical climate data, seasonal forecast and long term projections.

6.2.2.1 HISTORICAL CLIMATE

The 'Historical Climate' tab gives you the opportunity to consult historical monthly data for essential variables, like temperature and precipitation, bioclimatic indices and wine risk indicators. The available options (also illustrated in Figure 6-4) are:

1. Timescale(three different options)

Historical Climate: past and near-present information [Default and here selected]

Seasonal Forecast: predictions for the next six months

Long-Term Projections: future scenarios for the 21st century

2. Location (search by geographic coordinates, city or country)

3. Type of variables

Climate variables: temperature & precipitation monthly data

Bioclimatic indicators: indicators taking into account the climate and phenology of the vine, e.g. Growing Season Temperature (GST), Spring Rain (SprR), Harvest Rain (HarvestR), number of days with temperature higher than 35°C (SU35), Warm Spell Duration Index (WSDI)

Wine risk indicators: risk of diseases (Sanitary Risk) or heat damage (Heat Risk)

4. Region: region of interest (Douro or Iberian Peninsula).

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5. Variable of interest (hover over each variable for explanation)

6. Time period of interest

For the Douro Valley, PTHRES dataset (RD.4) is used, spanning 1951-2015, at 1 km of spatial resolution; PTHRES dataset was provided to MED-GOLD partners by University of Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro (UTAD). For the Iberian Peninsula, ERA5 dataset (RD.5) is used, spanning 1979-2020, at 31 km of spatial resolution (approximately) .

7. Filter: Data for each single year or averaged over the period 1981-2010

8. Export data. The maps can be exported in .csv (ascii format readable by spreadsheet applications like Microsoft Excel or OpenOffice), or .netcdf (standard for scientific computation., readable by basic Java application such as Panoply <https://www.giss.nasa.gov/tools/panoply/> , for example) or as images in .jpg format.

By clicking on the map (or by selecting a location in the above step #3) , a chart will appear with the time series of the requested field (see Fig. 6-5). The Time series can be printed or exported as csv file or as an image in .jpg or .png format.

Figure 6-5: Time series for a selected grid point in the Historical Climate tab

6.2.2.2 SEASONAL FORECAST

The Landing page for the 'Seasonal Forecast' Tab is reported in Fig.6-6. The predictions shown in the MED-GOLD Dashboard are the ECMWF SEAS5 seasonal predictions dataset obtained from the Climate Data Store of the Copernicus Climate Change Service (CDS-C3S) [RD.6].

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Figure 6-6: Landing page for the Seasonal Forecast tab

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1. Timescale

Historical Climate: past and near-present information

Seasonal Forecast: predictions for the next six months [HERE SELECTED]

Long-Term Projections: future scenarios for the 21st century

2. Location (search by geographic coordinates, city or country)

3. Type of variables

Climate variables: temperature & precipitation data

Bioclimatic indicators: indicators taking into account the climate and phenology of the vine, e.g. Growing Season Temperature (GST), Spring Rain (SprR), Harvest Rain (HarvestR), number of days with temperature higher than 35°C (SU35), Warm Spell Duration Index (WSDI)

Wine risk indicators: risk of diseases (Sanitary Risk) or heat damage (Heat Risk)

4. Variable of interest (hover over each variable for explanation)

5. Target period of the forecast

6. Starting Date: The "Starting Date" is the initial starting month of that specific forecast, i.e. when the forecast is issued.

7. Filter: Turn on the "Skill" filter option to hide areas where the prediction doesn't provide added value with respect to climatology (See RD.1 for major details)

8. Export data. The maps can be exported in .csv (ascii format readable by Microsoft Excel or OpenOffice), or .netcdf (standard for scientific computation., readable by basic Java application such as Panoply <https://www.giss.nasa.gov/tools/panoply/>) or as images in .jpg

Each prediction is portrayed in three categories or terciles: **above normal**, **normal** and **below normal**. Terciles are two values (lower and upper terciles) that divide a set of data (for example, the average temperature for the last 30 years) into three groups: one with the lowest 33% of values (those below the

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lower tercile or **below normal**), one with the highest 33% (those above the higher tercile or **above normal**) and the remaining 33%, centred around the middle value (**normal** value), between both terciles. In climate science, values that lie below the lower tercile (lowest 33%) or above the upper tercile (highest 33%) are commonly considered as anomalies.

These three baseline categories are obtained by looking at the past registers and distributing them in three classes according to their magnitude and frequency (the middle class or normal, the above normal and below normal). Afterwards the prediction is assigned to one of these three categories by comparing the predicted values with this distribution of historical registers. The map reported in Fig. 6-4 is a Dominant Tercile Summary Map that shows, on a single chart, the areas where a specific tercile probability is prevailing (exceeding 40%) over the others in the selected forecast. Such probabilities are computed by comparing the forecast probability density function (PDF) with the corresponding model climate PDF, estimated over the reference period (1993–2016). If the dominant tercile does not exceed 40% that grid point is not assigned to any tercile and it is not shown. This plot gives a convenient, simple overview of a seasonal forecast.

By clicking on the map (or by selecting a location in the above step #2) , a chart will appear with the time series of the observed / predicted categories for the requested field (see Fig. 6-7). The colored squares report the predicted most likely tercile (above normal, normal and below normal) while the blue dots are the percentiles for the reference observational dataset (ERA5). The time series can be printed or exported as .csv file or as an image.

Figure 6-7: Time series for a selected grid point in the Seasonal Forecast tab

6.2.2.3 LONG-TERM PROJECTIONS

The Landing page for the 'Long-term projections' Tab is reported in Figure 6-8.

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Figure 6-8: Landing page for the Long term projections tab

1. Timescale

Historical Climate: past and near-present information

Seasonal Forecast: predictions for the next six months

Long-Term Projections: future scenarios for the 21st century [HERE SELECTED]

2. Location (search by geographic coordinates, city or country)

3. Type of variables

Climate variables: temperature & precipitation data

Bioclimatic indicators: indicators taking into account the climate and phenology of the vine, e.g. Growing Season Temperature (GST), Spring Rain (SprR), Harvest Rain (HarvestR), number of days with temperature higher than 35°C (SU35), Warm Spell Duration Index (WSDI)

4. Select region: (Douro Valley or Andalusia)

The climate projections for the Douro valley have been downscaled and bias corrected using PTHRES (1km), while for the projections over Andalusia, EOBS-19 grd (around 11km) from a five member GCM-RCM sub-ensemble simulations from the EURO-CORDEX modelling experiment (<http://www.euro-cordex.net>) have been used. Major details in [RD.1]

5. Variable of interest (hover over each variable for explanation)

6. Target period of the projections: the time frame me for which to see future climate projections

7. Select the RCP (Future emission scenario): Scientists have defined different scenarios of how the emissions will change, known as the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs). The intermediate (RCP4.5) and high (RCP8.5) emission scenarios are available to select in the MED-GOLD dashboard, corresponding to a global temperature increase of 1.1-2.6°C and 2.6-4.8°C, respectively.

8. Filter: Data or anomalies It's possible to show the data for the time interval of interest or the deviation of the selected field from the long-term average value over the reference present climate 1971-2000.

9. Export data. The maps can be exported in .csv (ascii format readable by Microsoft Excel or OpenOffice), or .netcdf (standard for scientific computation, readable by basic Java application such as Panoply <https://www.giss.nasa.gov/tools/panoply/>) or as images in .jpg format.

6.3 HOW TO DOWNLOAD/INTERPRET THE RESULTS

Here we report some use cases drafted in order to facilitate the use and the interpretation of the MED-GOLD DASHBOARD for new users. These use cases have been also reported, as a basic tutorial, in the Infosheet (Annex A), which is also available in portuguese, spanish and greek.

6.3.1 USE CASE 1

You are a viticulturist. It's March, and you need to decide how much stock of plant protection products to buy this season. Rainy and warm springs can favour pest outbreaks in vines. Is this spring going to be particularly dry or wet? The following steps are also illustrated in Figure 6-9.

1. Start by selecting the "Seasonal Forecast" timescale, to check if this spring will be wetter than normal, normal or drier than normal in your area.
2. In bioclimatic variables, choose spring rain (SprR).
3. Select the current year.
4. Set the current month as the forecast Starting Date, which refers to the month when the forecast is issued.
5. Type in the geographical coordinates or the location of your cultivation site.
6. How accurate is the Prediction? Turn on the "Skill" filter option to hide areas where the prediction is not reliable enough for decision-making.
7. How well was spring rain predicted in the past? By clicking on the map, a chart will appear where circles correspond to values of spring rain observed in past years, and squares show model predictions (above normal, normal and below normal terciles).
 - Wetter than normal | upper tercile
 - Normal | medium tercile
 - Drier than normal | lower tercile
8. You can export the map and graph, discuss with the procurement department, and plan the purchase of plant protection products based on the seasonal forecasts and the prediction accuracy in your area in the past.

Figure 6-9: Snapshot of Use case 1

6.3.2 USE CASE 2

Your wine company is concerned about the impact that climate change will have on your top-selling iconic wine. The grape variety used has an optimal growth of 16-19°C. If your vineyard sees higher temperatures in the future, you will need to look for alternative sites to maintain your production. Is the quality of your iconic wine threatened by future climate change? The following steps are also illustrated in Figure 6-10.

1. First, select the "Long-term Projections" timescale.
2. In the location box, type in the name of the closest village to the vineyard
3. Select the growing season temperature (GST) from the bioclimatic indicators.
4. Then, select the time frame for which to see future temperatures (e.g. 2031-2060)
5. Finally, choose an emission scenario (e.g. intermediate greenhouse gas emissions)

In this situation, the average growing season temperature in the area is expected to be above 20 degrees Celsius, which is outside the range of your grape variety.

6. You can export the data from the map as a .csv table and use any spreadsheet application (e.g. Excel or OpenOffice) to find other geographical areas with more suitable temperatures to produce your top-selling wine in the future.

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Figure 6-10: Snapshot of Use case 2

7. CONTACT AND PENDING ISSUES

On the top right corner (Fig.6-9) of the homepage there is a feedback form to contact the development team about inquiries on the use of the Dashboard, bugs, possible suggestions and comments on the design and functionalities of the application. Every feedback could greatly help in further ameliorating the tool.

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Figure 6-11: Entry point for the Feedback form

The screenshot displays the MED-GOLD dashboard interface. On the left, there are navigation menus for 'Select Sector', 'Select Type' (with 'Bioclimatic' selected), 'Select Variable' (with 'GST' selected), 'Select Interval' (with '2031-2060' selected), 'Select RCP' (with 'Intermediate greenhouse gas emission' selected), and 'Filters'. The main area shows a map titled 'Projection - GST - 2031-2060' with a color-coded temperature projection overlay. A red box highlights a 'Leave your feedback' button in the top right corner of the map area. Below the map, a feedback form is overlaid, featuring a farm illustration, a 'Share Your feedback!' heading, a thank-you message, instructions, a Google account login prompt, a rating scale from 1 (Bad) to 5 (Excellent), and a 'Siguiente' button at the bottom.

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ANNEX A. THE MED-GOLD DASHBOARD INFOSHEET FOR THE WINE SECTOR

**WINE SECTOR &
CLIMATE CHANGE**

Grape and wine production is heavily affected by weather and climate. Climate change is causing extreme weather events, heatwaves and droughts, which have become a big challenge in recent years for grape growers and wine producers. As the climate continues to change in the future, anticipating such events is key for the adaptation of the wine sector.

Climate variability and climate change pose diverse challenges in the decision-making processes of wine producers, such as in defining long-term strategies, and in viticulture, oenological and stock management. Climate services, particularly predictions of climate variables and bioclimatic indices, can help in these decisions.

Read more on [Climate Services for the Grape and Wine Sector](#) in the MED-GOLD infosheet.

**MED-GOLD DASHBOARD
FOR THE WINE SECTOR**

The MED-GOLD dashboard is an easy-to-use visualisation tool for the wine sector, which provides access to information on past climate and predictions of future climate at different time scales. The tool has been co-developed with users to ensure that it addresses their needs and expectations.

You can access the dashboard on the MED-GOLD website, and by visiting: dashboard.med-gold.eu

ABOUT MED-GOLD

MED-GOLD is a 4-year European project on "Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional MEDiterranean Grape, OLive and Durum wheat food systems". MED-GOLD aims to make European agriculture and food systems more resilient, sustainable and efficient in the face of climate change by using climate services to minimize climate-driven risks and costs.

HOW TO USE THE MED-GOLD DASHBOARD

- 1 Select the sector icon
- 2 Timescale
 - **Historical Climate:** past and near-present information
 - **Seasonal Forecast:** predictions for the next months
 - **Long-Term Projections:** future scenarios for the 21st century
- 3 Location (search by geographic coordinates, city or country)

- 4 Type of variables
 - **Climate variables:** temperature & precipitation data
 - **Bioclimatic indicators:** indicators taking into account the climate and phenology of the vine, e.g. growing season temperature
 - **Wine risk indicators:** risk of diseases or heat damage
- 5 Variable of interest (hover over each variable for explanation)
- 6 Time period of interest
- 7 Other options/filters that change according to selected timescale, e.g. region of interest, forecast skill, greenhouse gas emission scenario
- 8 Export data

USE CASE 1

You are a viticulturist. It's February, and you need to decide how much stock of plant protection products to buy this season. Rainy and warm springs can favour pest outbreaks in vines.

Is this spring going to be particularly dry or wet?

1. Start by selecting the "Seasonal Forecast" timescale, to check if this spring will be **wetter than normal**, **normal** or **drier than normal** in your area.
2. In bioclimatic variables, choose spring rain (SprR).
3. Select the current year.
4. Set the current month as the forecast Starting Date, which refers to the month when the forecast is issued.
5. Type in the geographical coordinates or the location of your cultivation site.

RISK OF PESTS & DISEASES?

To better assess the risk of pests and diseases, you can also look at the temperature forecast in "Climate" variables alongside the spring rain information.

HOW ACCURATE IS THE PREDICTION?

Turn on the "Skill" filter option to hide areas where the prediction is not reliable enough for decision-making.

You can export the map and graph, discuss with the procurement department, and plan the purchase of plant protection products based on the seasonal forecasts and the prediction accuracy in your area in the past.

USE CASE 2

Your wine company is concerned about the impact that climate change will have on your top-selling iconic wine. The grape variety used has an optimal growth of 16-19°C. If your vineyard sees higher temperatures in the future, you will need to look for alternative sites to maintain your production.

Is the quality of your iconic wine threatened by future climate change?

1. First, select the "Long-term Projections" timescale.
2. In the location box, type in the name of the closest village to the vineyard
3. Select the growing season temperature (GST) from the bioclimatic indicators.
4. Then, select the time frame for which to see future temperatures (e.g. 2031-2060)
5. Finally, choose an emission scenario (e.g. intermediate greenhouse gas emissions)

In this situation, the average growing season temperature in the area is expected to be above 20 degrees Celsius, which is outside the range of your grape variety.

You can export the data from the map as a .csv table and use Excel to find other geographical areas with more suitable temperatures to produce your top-selling wine in the future.

DID YOU KNOW?
Greenhouse gas emissions (e.g. CO₂) are expected to rise in the future, increasing the global temperatures. Scientists have defined different scenarios of how the emissions will change, known as the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs). The intermediate (RCP4.5) and high (RCP8.5) emission scenarios are available to select in the MED-GOLD dashboard, corresponding to a global temperature increase of 1.1-2.6°C and 2.6-4.8°C, respectively.

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END OF DOCUMENT

A handy easy-to-use manual for stakeholders and practitioners of the
climate service tool.

PART II: the grape/ wine sector

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